

Impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This research investigated the impact of Concept-Mapping Instructional Strategy on Attitude and Performance in Algebra among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna Nigeria. A pretest posttest, quasi experimental design was used to carry out the study. A sample of 110 students, out of 2,345 mathematics students from two schools out of public senior secondary schools in the zone, was randomly selected. In this study, two research objectives were raised, two research questions were asked and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two research instruments were used in the study, namely: Algebraic Performance Test (APT) and Algebraic Attitudinal Questionnaire (AAQ). The two instruments were validated by experts. The reliability coefficients of APT and AAQ were calculated to be 0.81 and 0.79 respectively. Mean, Mean Rank, Standard Deviations were used to describe the data; while independent sample t-test, and Mann Whitney U- test were used in testing the hypothesis, the findings revealed that there is significant change in attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using concept mapping with their counterpart using lecture Method. More so, a significant difference in academic performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using concept mapping with those using lecture method in favor of the experimental group. The study concludes that the academic performance in algebra concepts can be enhanced significantly by the use of concept-mapping. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that Secondary School Mathematics teachers should frequently employ the use of concept mapping in teaching Algebra and other topics in mathematics.

Keywords: Concept-Mapping, Attitude, Instructional Strategy and Academic Performance

Introduction

Mathematics is regarded as a very important subject in the school curriculum, it is therefore imperative that special attention be paid to teaching of Mathematics topics such as algebra, indices, logarithms, calculus to mention a few. This study focused on the challenges that students face when learning algebra. More lessons are allocated for Mathematics as compared to other subjects, yet it has remained one of the worst performed subjects in the school syllabus. The Federal Government of Nigeria seems to have realized the importance of Mathematics as an important key for development by stating it's in National Policy on Education that the goals of Mathematics shall be "cultivate inquiring, knowing and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy" among other goals Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). This is in realization of the strength of inquiry in enhancing conceptual understanding in Mathematics. It is frequently used as a pump to many career opportunities and further education. Miheso (2014) noted that Mathematics competence opens doors to a productive future; a lack of mathematical competence keeps those doors closed. As a result, great pressure has been put on teachers of Mathematics to produce best results and again on the students' part to succeed in Mathematics more than in any other subjects. However, despite the urgent need for a good output in the Mathematical performance of students, the reverse is the case as students' academic performance continues to deteriorate year after year.

The expository sees the students as empty headed and they play an intellectually passive role. Although students become more active with the use of guided discovery methods, they are not really active in the sense of actively constructing knowledge (Aiyede, 2009). The continuous search for more effective strategies for teaching Mathematics concepts has led to focusing attention on how the learner learns and the learner's awareness of his cognitive processes as learning progresses. As noted by Cobbandin Aiyede (2009), Mathematics is both an individual constructive activity and a communal social practice. Since the teacher cannot provide whole class teaching and at the same time use a method that caters for individual differences

in learning, a choice of an adequate method must be made. It is conceivable that a small group learning strategy within which peers can learn from each other on a cooperative basis and under the supervision of the teacher might be a way out of this dilemma (Sadi, 2014).

An instructional strategy which focuses on the understanding and controlling of one's learning processes is needed. Agwagah and Ezeugo (2010) established on instructional theory, which is based on the Ausebel's meaningful learning idea that integrate concept maps to produce meaningful connections between the concepts in the learner's cognitive structure. According to Novak (2010), allows the teacher to create a more reflective, constructivist and also has transmissive learning environment. It involves students working together under the supervision of the teacher. Working in groups can help students to improve in the various aspects of their knowledge by providing comprehensive understanding on a given subject. It also limits memorization since it enables the learner to present the whole topic meaningfully with a few words (Adaramola, 2012). Thus, several teaching strategies could be used to teach algebra concepts depending on the concept to be taught. One of such strategies is the concept mapping strategy.

The concept-mapping instructional strategy is a kind of discovery method in which small groups are used. This learning strategy allows students in small groups to communicate with each other and it is believed that dialogue aids learning (Vygostky, 1978). The learning strategy is said to instill cooperative interaction in students, which results in improving learning (Aiyede, 2009). He also noted that the concept –mapping instructional strategy encourages collaboration among students. Thus, better understanding and higher achievements are enhanced. It is generally understood to be learning in which students work in small groups collectively by sharing ideas while working on a given task. Such a group presents special opportunities for active learning and an atmosphere for good communication (Novak, 2010). As a matter of fact, those who are proposing the restructuring of schools believe strongly that small group learning has the qualities that are essential for authentic achievement (Gongden and Delmong, 2016). Similarly; Electronic communication has become an integral part of our global society in which information can be circulated easily.

Thus, when students have a positive attitude toward Mathematics it will enhance good understanding of the concept taught. But the affective domain is often neglected because teachers have difficulty in designing strategies to develop positive attitude among students and documenting their development (Thomas and kobella, 2008). However, students' achievement also depends on attitudes that allow them to participate actively in the classroom (Liza, 2010). The students' attitude towards Mathematics needs to be assessed during the lesson so that the teacher can know how the students feel towards the teaching strategies, classroom activities and the subject matter. This will assist the teacher by providing an effective basis for developing useful educational innovation to facilitate Mathematics learning (Ado,2010). Muhammad (2014) said that teachers realize the importance of how the students feel about Mathematics subject and other courses; nevertheless, they place little emphasis on affective objectives.

Society is changing and instructional methods are no more adequate. Students lack a committed attitude to mathematics. Insufficient attention is not being given to the dimension of students' prior knowledge brought to the class that may influence this understanding. Thus, students' difficulties are traced to the quality of instruction and neglect of prior knowledge, which lead to misconception (Novak, 2010).

The review of this study was based on theoretical principles of meaningful learning; describe the process in which the learner deliberately chooses to relate new information to existing knowledge by assimilation through progressive differentiation and integration of new and old knowledge into existing knowledge structures through a degree of synthesis. (Ausubel, 2011 and Novak, 2004). It is argued that, making connections between old and new knowledge, may be cognitively facilitated by organizing and constructing, and visually communicated through maps/diagrams. Similarly, according to Piaget's (1968) theoretical model of cognitive development, humans naturally endeavor to arrange their thinking processes into the simplest structure possible which is known as schemas, progressively becoming blended and harmonized to become more sophisticated, complex structures. When thinking and cognitive processes grow into more complex ones, new schemas develop to enable greater adaptation to the environment. Piaget suggests that, even from birth, a person starts to search for occasions to adapt to the environment in a concise and efficient manner.

This adaptation or intellectual growth consists of three cognitive major processes: assimilation, accommodation, and equilibration. Assimilation entails the integration of new events into pre-existing cognitive structures. Accommodation involves existing structures being amended to accommodate the new information. This twofold process, assimilation-accommodation, allows the child to form schemas. Equilibration entails the person attaining a balance between the environment, assimilation and accommodation. According to Piaget, the delicate balancing action of organizing, assimilating, and accommodating occurs when real learning and cognitive growth take place. This is to say, the achievement of this search for equilibrium is crucial to cognitive structuring and development (Kemblitzky, 2009 and Mamba, 2012). Therefore, from a constructivist point of view,

for a teacher to support the student in the construction of his own knowledge, discussion, reflection and negotiation are essential approaches to teaching. Misconceptions are very important to learning and teaching, because they form part of a student's conceptual structure that will interact with new concepts. In general, concept maps are used as a graphical tool to create and show illustration the connection between ideas and concepts. It comprises two elements; namely the concepts-which are generally embedded in closed shapes together such as boxes and circles-and their connections, which are displayed as lines that connect the shape together. Concept maps are graphical tools or diagrams, which include concepts that are linked by lines that intend to represent meaningful relationships between concepts in the form of assertions or propositions.

Concept mapping is an example of meta-cognitive strategy of instruction, which involves focusing attention on how the learner learns and the learners' awareness of his cognitive processes as learning progresses, (Ahmad and Mirza, 2013). In other words, it focuses on the understanding and controlling of one's learning. It is an activity that can be best used by the teachers and students to make learning more meaningful. (Harris & Zha, 2014) they believe that the process of drawing a concept map makes the task of revision more active and can be used as a way to encourage group learning. They noted that through the use of concept maps relatively irrelevant concepts are not be-laboured and teacher's misconceptions are not taught to students. As a flexible tool, it can be applied in a variety of ways to improve the quality of learning.

Concept map is a drawing and a brief description of how someone or some group thinks that certain concepts are related. It summarizes how one group viewed the relationships among the different equations in algebra. Thus, concept maps consist of three elements; first concepts names written inside loops or rectangles; secondly linking lines as webbing activities or flow charts or arrows; and thirdly linking phrases describing the relationship. Concept maps illustrate the hierarchical order among ideas such that the most general concept is placed at the top. (Adaramola, 2012). Concept maps can also be in the form of spider maps, which are used to describe webbed relations. Thus, it involves the connection and drawing a concept map which requires explicitly defining connection, which can be an invaluable tool for fostering meaningful learning of mathematics by students at any level.

Novak & Gowin (1984) described the usefulness of concept mapping in enhancing problem solving skills. This is based on the attention focused by the relationships students perceive between ideas and how they structure those ideas. The use of concept maps can be carried out in a short period of time to achieve your impacts or goals, as outlined by Novak & Gowin (1984).

Impacts of Concept Mapping in Teaching Mathematics

Jonsson (2012) Concept begins from the earliest years of the child after which begins the internalization of new elements into the knowledge base causing differentiation of both new and original concepts as new associations are linked original concepts, jubrin & Zeyum (2012). As concepts become more sophisticated, the learner gains access to a wider range of applicability. To achieve full concept mapping, jonsson (2012) suggested that teachers should be at pains to train learners to think and help them to perceive and solve problems by themselves. The learner should be taught how to link related concepts properly. The understanding of the concepts will lead to problem solving through access to an organized knowledge base. Through this, knowledge is acquired as well as concepts are retained, Noss, et al (2013). Concepts are mental categories that help us classify objects, events, or ideas and each object, event, or idea has a set of common relevant features (Ratcliff, 2014). Thus, acquiring any knowledge the learner has to first acquire the necessary concepts that constitute the knowledge, (Tribuzi, 2015) The effects of concept mapping can be done through observation or by teaching. When a child begins to learn, he observes events or objects and is first taught by his parents. Thus, teaching is very crucial in concept mapping at secondary schools by the use of cooperative methods among students.

Cooperative learning instructional strategy requires a small number of students to work together on a common task, supporting and encouraging one another to improve their learning through interdependence and cooperation with one another (Larry & Hartman, 2009). It is generally understood that learning can be acquired where students work collaboratively in small groups by sharing ideas while working on a given task (Eniayeju, 2010). According to Wendy (2011) cooperative learning is the umbrella term for a variety of educational approaches involving joint intellectual effort by students, or students and teachers together. Each member of a group is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping others in the group to learn, creating an atmosphere of achievement. In cooperative learning, students work together in small groups on a structured activity. They are individually accountable for the work, and the work of the group as a whole is also assessed (Johnson, 2011). Therefore, this study investigates whether concept mapping strategies have an impact on attitude and performance in algebra among senior secondary schools' students in Zaria, Kaduna Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives for the study are to:

1. Investigate the impacts of concept mapping on the attitude of students toward Algebra.
2. Verify the effects of concept mapping on academic performance of students in Algebra.

Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the difference between the attitude mean ranks of students taught Algebra using concept-mapping and those taught with lecture methods?
2. How effective does the use of concept mapping result in better performance scores of students in Algebra than those uses of lecture method?

Null Hypotheses:

Based on the stated research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated for testing at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and their counterpart taught using lecture methods.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and their counterparts taught using lecture methods.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is a quasi-experimental which involves pretest, posttest experimental control groups. The population for this study consisted of all SSII mathematics students totaling 2,345 in public schools in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. The research is limited to SSII of the selected schools because of the stability and requires a lot of time to practice. From the population of Co-educational schools, two schools were selected randomly using purposive sampling. Intact classes were used with a total number of 102 students which constituted the sample. The 102-sample size was viable for the study in accordance with the Central Limit Theorem (CLT). The sample for this study is presented in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1 Sample for the study

s/n	Name of School	Group	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	EG1	31	27	58
2	School B	CG	28	16	44
Total			59	43	102

Algebraic Performance Test (APT) which was used for the pretest & posttest and Algebraic Attitude Questionnaire (AAQ) which was used to determine any students' attitude change in algebra which were the instruments developed and used in the study. After the treatment the data collected from the research questions were described using descriptive statistics that are mean, standard deviation and mean differences. For both pretest and posttest in experimental and control groups were analyzed using inferential statistical tools. The null hypotheses will be tested at ≤ 0.05 level of significance to answer stated hypotheses: HO₁, was tested using Mann Whitney U- test and HO₂ was tested using independent t-test.

Presentation of Results

Answering the Research Questions and Hypotheses Testing

Question One: What is the difference between the attitude mean ranks of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and those taught using Lecture method?

To find out the effects of Concept Mapping on students' attitude in Algebra at senior secondary schools' level, the mean attitude level of students taught Algebra using concept mapping and that of conventional lecture method were computed and compared as presented in Table 1.2

Table 1.2: Mean Rank, Sum of Rank Statistics of Posttest Attitude level for Students after exposed to Concept Mapping (EG1) and Lecture Method (CG)

GROUP	N	Mean	Sum of Ranks
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EG1	58	73.50	4263.00
CG	44	22.50	990.00
Total	102		

The Outcome of the Non-Parametric test in Table 1.2 above revealed that there is a difference between mean attitude level of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method. Their computed mean rank attitude levels are 73.50 and 22.50 by SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method respectively indicating a mean rank difference of 51 in favour of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. This implies that the use of Concept Mapping has a higher positive effect in the level of attitude towards learning Algebra than their counterpart taught lecture method.

Hypothesis Testing 1

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between attitude mean rank students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method.

Mean rank response on attitude towards the teaching and learning of the subject in Table 1.2 were compared to determine the significant difference using the Mann Whitney U-test. The result of the test is summarized in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3: Summary of Mann Whitney Test of students' Posttest Attitude Mean Rank between Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

GROUP	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	P	Decision
EG1	58	73.50	4263.00	0.000	S
CG	44	22.50	990.00		
Total	102				

$p = 0.000 < 0.05$ alpha level of significance

Table 1.3 revealed that significant differences exist between the attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method. This is because the calculated p- value of 0.000 was lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. Their computed Mean Rank attitude levels are 73.50 and 22.50 by SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method respectively indicating a Mean Rank difference of 51 in favour of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant difference between the attitude mean rank of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterpart taught using Lecture method is hereby rejected in favour of the experimental group.

Question Two: How effective does the use of concept mapping result in better performance scores of students in Algebra than those uses of Lecture method?

To find out the effects of concept mapping on the academic performance of students in the selected schools, performance of the two groups (Concept Mapping and Lecture) were computed and compared. The mean scores for the two groups on the subject are tabulated in Table 1.4 below.

Table 1.4: Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics of Posttest scores for Students after exposed to Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference
EG1	58	33.59	2.35	7.04
CG	44	26.55	2.36	

Results in Table 1.4 showed that a difference exists between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method. Their computed mean performances are 33.59 and 26.55 of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using

Lecture method respectively, with a mean performance difference of 7.04 in favour of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping.

Hypothesis Testing 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method. To test this hypothesis, the performance scores of students exposed to the use of the concept mapping and those taught with lecture methods were computed and compared. Independence t-test was used to test the hypothesis and the result is presented in Table 1.5

Table 1.5: Summary of Independent Sample t-test of Mean Posttest Scores of students for Experimental Group (EG1) and Control Group (CG)

Group	N	Mean	STD	Mean diff.	df	p	Decision
EG1	58	33.59	2.35	7.04	100	0.000	S
CG	44	26.55	2.36				

Table 1.5 showed a significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using the Lecture method. Reasons being that the calculated p-value of 0.00 was <0.05 alpha level of significance. Their computed mean performances are 33.59 and 26.55 of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method respectively, with a mean performance difference of 7.04 in favour of students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of SSII mathematics students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method, is hereby rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the two groups. Thus, students exposed to concept mapping performed significantly better than the students taught using lecture methods.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the two null hypotheses tested in this study towards determining the impacts of Concept Mapping instructional strategies on attitude and performance in Algebra among selected Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria, Kaduna State Nigeria are discussed as follows:

The finding from the test of hypothesis 1 showed that students in the experimental groups had a higher attitude mean rank level than those in the control group. The difference was significant as indicated by the Mann Whitney U-test in Table 1.2. This signifies that students taught algebraic concepts using Concept Mapping had a significantly higher mean attitude level than those taught using Lecture Method. By implication, the Concept Mapping was able to foster a significantly higher attitude than the Lecture Method. The significant difference implies rejection of null hypotheses and retaining alternate hypotheses. Therefore, null hypotheses which state that there is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using Lecture method are rejected. The significant difference indicates that students in experimental groups recorded the highest mean score than those in the Lecture Method. This finding supports the findings of Akinsola and Awofala (2004) showed the usefulness of concept mapping in improving students' attitudes and reducing anxiety in learning mathematics. The finding is in line with Laight (2006) who showed that concept mapping is very useful in interactive environments. These researches revealed that students exhibited significant improvements in attitude as a result of treatment with Concept Mapping as compared to the Lecture method.

The results analysis of the test scores of hypotheses two revealed that students in the experimental groups had a higher mean performance score than those in the control group. The difference was significant as indicated by the independent t-test in Table 1.5. This signifies that student taught algebra concepts using Concept Mapping had significantly higher mean performance scores than those taught using Lecture Method. By implication, the Concept Mapping was able to foster a significantly higher performance than the Lecture Method. The finding agrees with the report of Aderamola (2012) on his study investigating the effects of concept mapping on the performance and interest of students with dyscalculia in mathematics. This is also in line with the findings of Usman and Musa (2019). The findings revealed that; students in the concept mapping method group performed significantly better and were more interested in mathematics. Similarly, Therefore, null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of SSII students taught Algebra using Concept Mapping and their counterparts taught using the Lecture method. The significant difference indicates that students in experimental groups

recorded the highest mean score than those in the Lecture Method. These findings revealed that students exhibited significant improvements in performance as a result of treatment with Concept Mapping as compared to the Lecture method.

Conclusion

The findings of these studies were based on the attitude of students that can be fostered significantly by the use of Concept Mapping. Academic performance in Algebraic concepts can be enhanced significantly by the use of Concept Mapping and attitude toward learning concepts; it is also promoted by the use of Concept Mapping which improves their motivation by seeing the relationships between the concepts being used.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Professional bodies like MAN, STAN in collaboration with the Federal and State Ministries of Education should embark on nationwide re-training of Mathematics teachers to design and implement classroom instructions based on the Concept Mapping through regular national, state and local seminars, workshops and conferences.
2. Secondary school Mathematics teachers should frequently employ the Concept Mapping in teaching difficult and abstract concepts in Mathematics like Algebra.
3. Mathematics teachers should consistently encourage students to actively participate in Concept Mapping explorations, discussions and elaboration of learnt concepts for better academic performance and attitude towards learning mathematics.

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